

Evidence for an LKB1/AMPK/eNOS Cascade Regulated by HGF, S-Adenosylmethionine and NO in Hepatocyte Proliferation

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ABSTRACT

S-Adenosylmethionine (SAME) is involved in numerous complex hepatic processes such as hepatocyte proliferation, death, inflammatory responses, and anti-oxidant defense. One of the most relevant actions of SAME is the inhibition of hepatocyte proliferation during liver regeneration. In hepatocytes, SAME regulates the levels of cytoplasmic HuR, an RNA-binding protein that increases the half-life of target mRNA such as cyclin D1 and A2, via inhibition of HGF-mediated AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) phosphorylation. Because AMPK is activated by the tumor suppressor kinase LKB1, and AMPK activates endothelial nitric oxide (NO) synthase (eNOS), and NO synthesis is of great importance for hepatocyte proliferation, we hypothesized that in hepatocytes HGF may induce the phosphorylation of LKB1, AMPK and eNOS through a process regulated by SAME, and that this cascade might be crucial for hepatocyte growth. Here we demonstrate that the proliferative response of hepatocytes involves eNOS phosphorylation via HGF-mediated LKB1 and AMPK phosphorylation, and that this process is regulated by SAME and NO. We also show that knockdown of LKB1, AMPK, or eNOS with specific iRNA inhibits HGF-mediated hepatocyte proliferation. Finally, we found that the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade is activated during liver regeneration after partial hepatectomy and that this process is impaired in mice treated with SAME before hepatectomy, in knockout mice deficient in hepatic SAME, and in eNOS knockout mice. **Conclusion**—We have identified an LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade regulated by HGF, SAME and NO that functions as a critical determinant of hepatocyte proliferation during liver regeneration after partial hepatectomy.

Keywords: LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade; S-adenosylmethionine; nitric oxide; hepatocyte growth factor; liver proliferation

INTRODUCTION

Hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) induces hepatocyte proliferation and plays an essential role in liver regeneration^{1,2}. HGF activates the MET receptor signaling cascade, which includes the activation of the Ras/ERK/mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), PI3K/Akt, Rac/ Pak, and Crk/Rap1 pathways^{3,4}. Activation of the Ras/ERK/MAPK response is of great importance for HGF-induced hepatocyte proliferation^{5,6}. We have uncovered an alternative noncanonical pathway for HGF signaling associated with AMPK, which is also of great importance for HGF-induced hepatocyte proliferation⁷. AMPK is a serine/threonine kinase that was initially characterized as a sensor of cellular energy status that is activated in response to cellular stresses that deplete energy stores –such as hypoxia- switching-on metabolic pathways that generate ATP while switching-off metabolic pathways that consume ATP⁸. More recent studies have implied AMPK in a wider role of cellular processes including cell proliferation, angiogenesis and inflammation⁸. AMPK is activated by phosphorylation by at least two upstream kinases, the tumor suppressor kinase LKB1 and Ca²⁺/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase kinase⁹⁻¹¹. We have found that activation of AMPK by HGF in hepatocytes stimulates the transport from nucleus to cytoplasm of HuR⁷, an RNA-binding protein that increases the half-life of target mRNAs such as cyclin A2 and D1^{12,13}. We found also that SAME, the main biological methyl donor and a precursor of glutathione synthesis^{14,15}, inhibits these effects

of HGF on AMPK activation and HuR translocation, as well as HGF-induced cyclin D1 and D2 expression, DNA synthesis and hepatocyte proliferation, through a process that involves the association of PP2A to AMPK⁷.

SAME biosynthesis is catalyzed by methionine adenosyltransferase (MAT), the first step in methionine metabolism^{14,15}. Of the two genes (MAT1A, MAT2A) that encode MAT, MAT1A is expressed in adult liver^{14,15}. MAT1A knockout (MAT1A-KO) mice have chronic hepatic SAME deficiency, display increased proliferation, and spontaneously develop hepatocellular carcinoma^{16,17}. We found that in mice lacking MAT1A, liver AMPK is hyperphosphorylated⁷. We also observed, that HuR's cytoplasmic content, the binding of HuR to cyclin A2 and D1, and the steady-state levels of these two mRNA, were all increased in MAT1A-KO animals compared to WT mice liver⁷.

Cellular SAME is related to the growth status of the hepatocytes. Thus, quiescent and proliferating hepatocytes display different SAME contents, being lower in the growing cells¹⁸. This has been observed in rat liver following partial hepatectomy (PH), a commonly used experimental model for the analysis of liver regeneration^{2,5,6}, after which the content of SAME is reduced subsequent to the intervention, coinciding with the induction of early-response genes and the onset of DNA synthesis¹⁹⁻²¹. When the decrease in liver SAME after PH is prevented by the administration of exogenous SAME, the regenerative process is also impaired as a result of an insufficient proliferative response²¹. The decrease in hepatic SAME during liver regeneration is mediated by the peak in NO production that occurs in the liver after PH²²⁻²⁴. NO regulates hepatocyte SAME content through specific inactivation of hepatic MAT via S-nitrosylation of a cysteine residue (C121) of the enzyme^{25,26}.

In endothelial cells, AMPK has been shown to phosphorylate and activate endothelial NO synthase (eNOS)²⁷⁻³⁰ and, also in vascular endothelial cells, HGF stimulates NO production through eNOS phosphorylation^{31,32}. NO is important for the proliferative response of the liver, because inhibition of NOS activity with L-NAME results in decreased hepatocyte proliferation after PH³³ and prevents hepatocyte proliferation in response to HGF³⁴. Moreover, liver regeneration is impaired in inducible NOS (iNOS) knockout mice²⁴. eNOS has been identified at the plasma membrane, rough endoplasmic reticulum and in the nuclei of rat hepatocytes; and lysophosphatidic acid (LPA) has been shown to stimulate the phosphorylation of eNOS and NO production, as well as the induction of iNOS gene expression³⁵. This increase in iNOS expression was abrogated in eNOS knockout (eNOS-KO) mice, indicating that endogenous NO synthesized by eNOS mediates iNOS induction upon stimulation with LPA³⁵.

Here we demonstrate that in mice the proliferative response of hepatocytes involves eNOS phosphorylation and NO production via HGF-mediated LKB1 and AMPK phosphorylation, and that this process is regulated by SAME. Thus, PH may provoke liver injury, rather than liver regeneration, when eNOS activation is prevented.

Methods

Isolation and Culture of Hepatocytes

Hepatocytes were isolated from male C57BL6 mouse by collagenase perfusion as described³⁶. Two-hours after cells were plated, the medium was replaced by MEM supplemented with 5% FBS, and treatments were carried out after 2-hours. Details are given on line.

Immunoblot Analysis

Samples were separated by SDS-PAGE and analyzed by immunoblotting using commercial antibodies.

Confocal Microscopy

Hepatocytes were plated onto round cover slips at 1×10^6 cells/60-mm dish. After 2-hours, hepatocytes were washed twice with PBS and HGF (25 ng/ml) and/or SAME (4 mM) was added. One-hour later cells were fixed in ethanol 100% for 10 min at room temperature, rinsed twice with PBS buffer and kept in PBS-sodium azide. Details are given on line.

Gene Silencing

MLP29 cells, a hepatocyte cell line³⁷, were transfected with iRNA (Qiagen) for gene silencing using Lipofectamine 2000 (Invitrogen). After 16-hours, the medium was replaced with fresh DMEM, 5% FBS for another 8-hours and left overnight in DMEM, 0.1% FBS. Cells were then treated with HGF (25 ng/ml) for 4-hours for Western blot assay. Details are given on line.

DNA Synthesis

MLP29 cells were transfected with iRNA as described above. For each transfection 5000 cells were placed in a 96 well plate. Medium was replaced 24-hours after transfection with fresh DMEM, 5% FBS. After 4-hours

medium was replaced with DMEM, 0.1% FBS and left overnight at 37°C. Cells were treated with HGF (25 ng/ml) and for the last 10-hours (³H)-thymidine (0.5 µCi/well) was added. Cells were harvested and thymidine incorporation was determined in a scintillation counter. For non-transfected cell experiments, 1000 cells were plated and the protocol used was as described before.

Partial Hepatectomy Experiments

Two-third PH was performed, by the method of Higgins and Andersen³⁹, in 2- to 3-month-old male WT mice, WT animals pretreated with SAME (50mg/kg i.p. SAME, 3 times at 12-hours intervals, last dose 30 min before 2/3 PH), MAT1A-KO¹⁶ and eNOS-KO³⁸ mice as previously described⁴⁵. Two hours before sacrifice, mice were injected i.p. with bromodeoxyuridine (BrdU, 100 mg/kg body weight) to assess hepatocyte DNA synthesis as described⁴⁵. Details are given on line.

BrdU Immunohistochemistry

Frozen liver tissue sections were fixed with acetone for 1 min at room temperature followed by treatment with 2 M HCl at 37°C for 20 min. The sections were then neutralised with 0.1 M sodium borate for 10 min and mouse monoclonal anti-BrdU antibody (Roche Diagnostics, UK) applied overnight at 4°C followed by goat anti-mouse Rhodamine antibody (Cappel, PA, USA) and Hoescht nuclear dye. The number of BrdU positive cells was counted and expressed as a percentage of total number of cells, as visualized by Hoescht labeling.

NO and SAME Measurement

NO was determined in the culture medium of hepatocytes or MLP29 cells using a Nitric Oxide Assay Kit (Assay Designs). Hepatocytes and MLP29 cells were plated for 12-hours in MEM media containing 0.1% FBS. At the end of this period, cells were incubated for 4-hours in the presence or absence of HGF (25 ng/ml) and NO determined in the culture medium. Hepatic SAME was determined as described previously⁴⁰.

Statistical analysis

Student *t* test was used to evaluate statistical significance. Values of *p* < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

HGF Induces LKB1/AMPK/eNOS Phosphorylation Through a Process Inhibited by SAME

We have previously demonstrated that, in hepatocytes, HGF induces the phosphorylation and activation of AMPK and that SAME blocks this process probably via the activation of phosphoprotein phosphatases⁷. Because AMPK is activated by the tumor suppressor kinase LKB1¹⁸, we hypothesized that in hepatocytes HGF may induce also the phosphorylation of LKB1. We found that 1-hour after the addition of HGF to hepatocytes the phosphorylation of LKB1 and AMPK was induced without affecting the protein content of both kinases and that this effect remained for at least 4-hours (Fig. 1a). Since AMPK has been found to mediate the phosphorylation of eNOS²⁷⁻³⁰ and this enzyme is expressed in rat hepatocyte³⁵, we also examined the phosphorylation of eNOS in response to HGF in hepatocytes. We observed that 1-hour after the addition of HGF, the phosphorylation of eNOS was increased without affecting the protein content of the enzyme and that this effect remained for at least 4-hours (Fig. 1a). Since ERK can phosphorylate LKB1 via p90RSK41, we used U0126, an ERK1/2 inhibitor⁴², to determine if LKB1, AMPK and/or eNOS are or not targets of MAPK or another MET associated kinase. U0126 addition to hepatocytes inhibited both basal and HGF-induced ERK1/2 phosphorylation (Fig. 1b). By the contrary, U0126 did not inhibit but increased basal LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation (Fig. 1b). HGF-mediated phosphorylation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS pathway was less pronounced in U0126 treated cells than in control cells (Fig. 1b), as might be expected to be the case since this pathway was already activated in U0126 treated cells before the addition of HGF. We also found, that treatment with SAME blocked the effect of HGF on LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation (Fig. 1c). Further we confirmed by confocal microscopy that, within 1-hour, HGF-induced eNOS phosphorylation in hepatocytes and that SAME treatment blocked this effect (Fig. 2). These results support the hypothesis that the LKB1 pathway is not downstream of ERK but is an alternative pathway, downstream of MET, that is distinct from the Ras/ERK/MAPK pathway and is regulated by SAME.

We have previously shown that the inhibitory effect of SAME on HGF-induced AMPK phosphorylation in mouse hepatocytes is prevented by calyculin A, an inhibitor of PP2A and PP1⁷. Here we found that the inhibitory effect of SAME on HGF-induced LKB1 and eNOS phosphorylation is also blocked by calyculin A (Fig. 1d). We also found that 2.5 nM okadaic acid, another inhibitor of PP2A and PP1 activity⁷, also blocked the inhibitory effect of SAME on HGF-induced LKB1 and eNOS phosphorylation (data not shown). Taken together, these results support

the concept that SAME prevents HGF-mediated LKB1/ AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation through a process that involves the activation of phosphoprotein phosphatases.

HGF-induced LKB1/AMPK/eNOS Phosphorylation and Proliferation is Regulated by NO

NO is important for the proliferative response of the liver, because inhibition of NOS activity with L-NAME results in decreased hepatocyte proliferation after PH³³ and prevents hepatocyte proliferation in response to HGF³⁴. Moreover, liver regeneration after PH is impaired in inducible NOS (iNOS) knockout mice²⁴; and SAME, which blocks HGF-dependent hepatocyte proliferation³⁴, inhibits iNOS expression⁴³. eNOS has been identified at the plasma membrane, rough endoplasmic reticulum and in the nuclei of rat hepatocytes, and the activation of liver eNOS by LPA has been found to induce iNOS expression and NO production³⁵. Since in hepatocytes NO reduces SAME content through inhibition of its synthesis^{25,26} and treatment with L-NAME results in increased SAME synthesis and content in these cells³⁴, we hypothesized that NOS inhibition would prevent both HGF-mediated LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation and proliferation. Accordingly, we observed that in mouse hepatocytes L-NAME and N-iminoethyl-L-ornithine (NIO), another inhibitor of NOS activity⁴⁴, both inhibited HGF-mediated phosphorylation of LKB1/AMPK/eNOS and proliferation (Fig. 1c, Fig. 3a,b). These results indicate that, in hepatocytes, NO regulates HGF-mediated LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation and that eNOS activity is important for hepatocyte proliferation.

Inhibition of HGF-mediated Hepatocyte Proliferation by Knockdown of LKB1, AMPK and eNOS

To examine if the proliferative response of hepatocytes involves eNOS phosphorylation via HGF-mediated LKB1 and AMPK phosphorylation, we used iRNA to reduce the expression of LKB1, the AMPK α 1 catalytic subunit, and eNOS. For these experiments we used MLP29 cells, which are easier to transfect with iRNA than primary cultures of hepatocytes⁷. First we observed that transfection with LKB1-, AMPK α 1-, and eNOS-specific iRNA led to a marked reduction in LKB1, AMPK α 1, and eNOS protein levels as compared to cells transfected with control iRNA (Fig. 4a). Then we observed that whereas in MLP29 cells transfected with control iRNA the addition of HGF induced AMPK and eNOS phosphorylation, in cells transfected with LKB1-specific iRNA the effect of HGF on AMPK and eNOS phosphorylation was prevented (Fig. 4b). Similarly, transfection with AMPK α 1-specific iRNA prevented the phosphorylation of eNOS induced by HGF but had no effect on LKB1 phosphorylation, supporting the hypothesis that LKB1 is upstream AMPK (Fig. 4b). Finally, we observed that while HGF induced the proliferation of MLP29 cells transfected with control iRNA, in cells transfected with LKB1-, AMPK α 1-, or eNOS-specific iRNA the proliferative response induced by HGF was prevented (Fig. 5). In endothelial cells, HGF stimulates NO production through phosphorylation of eNOS^{32,33}. Accordingly, we found that in MLP29 cells, transfected with control iRNA, HGF (25 ng/ml) induced the production of NO to the culture medium (from $6.4 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{mol/L}$ in control cells to $9.2 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{mol/L}$ in cells treated with HGF, $p < 0.05$, $n = 4$) and that this effect was blocked in MLP29 cells transfected with eNOS-specific iRNA (from $6.4 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{mol/L}$ in control cells to $6.5 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{mol/L}$ in cells treated with HGF, $n = 4$). In hepatocytes, the production of NO to the culture medium was also induced by HGF (from $48.9 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{mol/L}$ in control cells to $73.7 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{mol/L}$ in cells treated with HGF, $p < 0.05$, $n = 4$). All together, these results indicate that HGF induces the activation of an LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade that may be of great importance for HGF-induced hepatocyte proliferation.

Phosphorylation of LKB1, AMPK and eNOS During Liver Regeneration After Partial Hepatectomy: Inhibition by SAME

To strengthen the concept that HGF-mediated phosphorylation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade is of great importance for hepatocyte proliferation and plays an essential role in liver regeneration, we have examined liver LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation following PH in control mice, in mice treated with SAME, to prevent the reduction in hepatic SAME after PH²⁰, and in MAT1A-KO animals deficient in hepatic SAME¹⁶. It is known that HGF levels rise significantly in the blood within 5 minutes after PH and that MET receptor phosphorylation occurs within 30 minutes and is high at 30 minutes to 1-hour after PH^{5,6}. Consistently, we found that the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade is phosphorylated within 30 minutes after PH and that this effect was maintained during the next 24-hours (Fig. 6a), suggesting that this pathway is part of the early-response during liver regeneration.

Previous work has shown that liver regeneration after PH is impaired both in SAME treated animals²¹ and in SAME deficient MAT1A-KO mice⁴⁵. Here we found, that phosphorylation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade was blocked in SAME treated animals (Fig. 6b). SAME treatment, however, had no effect on the expression levels of

liver MET (data not shown), which agrees with previous results showing that, in hepatocytes, SAME has no effect on HGF-dependent MET and ERK1/2 phosphorylation^{34,46}. In MAT1A-KO mice deficient in hepatic SAME, basal liver phosphorylation of LKB1 and AMPK was augmented but failed to increase further following PH (Fig. 6b). We observed also that although basal eNOS phosphorylation was normal in MAT1A-KO mice liver, after PH failed to increase (Fig. 6b). Finally, we observed that in eNOS-KO mice, LKB1 and AMPK phosphorylation following PH was prevented (Fig. 6b). We also observed that, after PH, hepatocyte growth, measured by BrdU incorporation, was markedly reduced in WT mice treated with SAME and in eNOS-KO mice (Fig. 6c).

We have previously demonstrated that liver SAME decreases after PH in WT mice but not in MAT1A-KO animals where, before PH, SAME content is already about half that measured in control animals⁴⁵. Before PH, hepatic SAME content was similar in WT and eNOS-KO mice (0.36 ± 0.04 and 0.35 ± 0.04 nmol/mg protein respectively, $n=4$), but was about 2-fold higher in SAME treated animals (0.68 ± 0.09 nmol/mg protein, $n=4$). Twenty-four hours after PH hepatic SAME content decreased in WT and eNOS-KO mice (0.23 ± 0.03 and 0.19 ± 0.02 nmol/mg protein respectively, $n=4$) and, although also decreased in SAME treated animals (0.34 ± 0.03 nmol/mg protein, $n=4$), the levels in this model remained essentially as those in WT mice before PH, indicating that there is a correlation between SAME levels and the inhibitory effects observed on the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS pathway.

Summing up, these results suggest that activation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade is of great importance for hepatocyte proliferation during liver regeneration and stress the crucial role of SAME in this process.

Discussion

Previous studies have emphasized the role of activation of the Ras/ERK/MAPK pathway in HGF-induced hepatocyte proliferation and liver regeneration after partial hepatectomy¹⁻⁶. The present study has uncovered a noncanonical pathway for HGF-induced hepatocyte proliferation. We have identified an LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade regulated by HGF, SAME and NO that functions as a critical determinant of hepatocyte proliferation during liver regeneration after partial hepatectomy. This conclusion is based, mainly, in the finding that HGF induces the phosphorylation of LKB1, AMPK and eNOS; and in the observation that knockdown of LKB1, AMPK or eNOS, prevents HGF-induced hepatocyte proliferation. The finding that the inhibition of the Ras/ERK/MAPK pathway with U0126 did not inhibit but increased basal LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation suggests that this cascade is not downstream ERK, but is an alternative pathway downstream of MET that is distinct from the Ras/ERK/MAPK pathway. The present results also strengthen our hypothesis that SAME is a central regulator of hepatocyte proliferation^{14,15}, and point to the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade as its main site of action. Our results demonstrate that, in hepatocytes, SAME prevents HGF-mediated phosphorylation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade through a mechanism that probably involves phosphoprotein phosphatase activation. Accordingly, we observed that phosphorylation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade in mice liver increases during liver regeneration after PH, but that this increase is prevented by the administration of SAME to mice prior to hepatectomy, which agrees with previous findings showing that SAME treatment impairs the liver regenerative process²¹. We found also that LKB1 and AMPK are hyperphosphorylated in MAT1A-KO mice liver, which agrees with our observation that the content of cytoplasmic HuR, a target of AMPK in the liver, the binding of HuR to cyclin A2 and cyclin D1, the steady-state levels of these two mRNA, and DNA synthesis are all increased in the liver of MAT1A-KO animals compared to WT mice⁷. In MAT1A-KO, after PH the phosphorylation of LKB1, AMPK and eNOS failed to increase, which agrees with the finding that hepatic SAME content did not fall further in MAT1A-KO mice as compared to WT⁴⁵, and is consistent with our previous observation showing that liver regeneration after PH is impaired in MAT1A-KO mice, and with the finding that hepatocytes isolated from these knockout animals do not respond to HGF⁴⁵.

NO production plays an important role in liver regeneration. After PH, liver regeneration is impaired in mice lacking iNOS²⁴, and the inhibition of NOS activity with L-NAME reduces hepatocyte proliferation after PH³³ as well as prevents hepatocyte proliferation in response to HGF³⁴. It has recently been shown, that the hepatic increase in iNOS expression elicited by LPA is abrogated in eNOS-KO mice, indicating that endogenous NO synthesized by eNOS mediates iNOS induction³⁵. Additionally, it has been found that HuR binds and stabilizes iNOS in hepatocytes^{47,48}, and that SAME prevents iNOS induction in liver and hepatocytes in response to bacterial lipopolysaccharide and proinflammatory cytokines⁴³. Here we found that HGF induces eNOS phosphorylation in hepatocytes and that after eNOS knockdown, with specific iRNA, hepatocyte proliferation in response to HGF was markedly reduced. These findings support a model (Fig. 7) where NO, generated by the combined action of eNOS and iNOS, inhibits hepatic SAME synthesis^{25,26} and releases the blocking effect this molecule exerts on the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS pathway and, consequently, stimulates the translocation of HuR from the nucleus to the cytoplasm leading to cell cycle progression and hepatocyte proliferation as well as to further stimulation of NO

production. The observation that inhibition of NO synthesis with L-NAME or NIO prevents HGF-induced LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation and proliferation agrees with this model since, in the absence of an increased production of NO synthesis in response to HGF, SAME synthesis will not be inhibited and the blockade this molecule exerts on LKB1/AMPK/eNOS phosphorylation will be maintained. Supporting this view, and the importance of eNOS-generated NO in the regulation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade by HGF, in eNOS-KO mice after PH the phosphorylation of LKB1 and AMPK failed to increase and liver regeneration was markedly impaired. The mechanism by which HGF/MET signaling increases LKB1 phosphorylation is not understood. MET might associate with and phosphorylate LKB1, or do so through another intermediate kinase (other than ERK).

Interestingly, protein kinase C activates LKB1 in endothelial cells⁴⁹, and protein kinase C inhibition impairs HGF-induced MAP-kinase activation in hepatocytes⁵⁰. Alternatively, it is also possible that MET inactivates a phosphatase allowing for increased LKB1 phosphorylation. Interestingly, PP2A associates with MET in A549 cells⁵¹.

In summary, here we demonstrate that the proliferative response of hepatocytes involves eNOS phosphorylation and NO production via HGF-mediated LKB1 and AMPK phosphorylation, and that this process is regulated by SAME. In addition to its mitogenic effect, HGF regulates many other signaling pathways including motility, survival and morphogenesis⁶. Whether the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade plays a role in these other pathways needs to be investigated.

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REFERENCES

1. Birchmeier C, Birchmeier W, Gherardi E, Vande Woude GF. Met, metastasis, motility and more. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol.* 2003; 4:915–925. [PubMed: 14685170]
2. Borowiak M, Garratt AN, Wüstefeld T, Strehle M, Trautwein C, Birchmeier C. Met provides essential signals for liver regeneration. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2004; 101:10608–10613. [PubMed: 15249655]
3. Ponzetto C, Bardelli A, Zhen Z, Maina F, dalla Zonca P, Giordano S, Graziani A, Panayotou G, Comoglio PM. A multifunctional docking site mediates signaling and transformation by the hepatocyte growth factor/scatter factor receptor family. *Cell.* 1994; 77:261–277. [PubMed: 7513258]
4. Paumelle R, Tulasne D, Kherrouche Z, Plaza S, Leroy C, Reveneau S, Vandebunder B, Fafeur V. Hepatocyte growth factor/scatter factor activates the ETS1 transcription factor by a RAS-RAF-MEK-ERK signaling pathway. *Oncogene.* 2002; 21:2309–2319. [PubMed: 11948414]
5. Fausto N, Campbell JS, Riehle KJ. Liver regeneration. *Hepatology.* 2006; 43:S45–53. [PubMed: 16447274]
6. Michalopoulos GM. Liver regeneration. *J Cell Physiol.* 2007; 213:286–300. [PubMed: 17559071]
7. Martínez-Chantar ML, Vázquez-Chantada M, Garnacho M, Latasa MU, Varela-Rey M, Dotor J, Santamaría M, Martínez-Cruz LA, Parada LA, Lu SC, Mato JM. S-adenosylmethionine regulates cytoplasmic HuR via AMPK-activated kinase. *Gastroenterology.* 2006; 131:223–232. [PubMed: 16831604]
8. Hardie DG, Hawley SA, Scott JW. AMP-activated protein kinase-development of the energy sensory concept. *J Physiol.* 2006; 574:7–15. [PubMed: 16644800]
9. Hawley SA, Boudeau J, Reid JL, Mustard KJ, Udd L, Makela TP, Alessi DR, Hardie DG. Complexes between the LKB1 tumor suppressor, STRAD α/β are upstream kinases in the AMP-activated protein kinase cascade. *J Biol.* 2003; 2:28. [PubMed: 14511394]
10. Hawley SA, Pan DA, Mustard KJ, Ross L, Bain J, Edelman AM, Frengueli BG, Hardie DG. Calmodulin-dependent protein kinase-beta is an alternative upstream kinase for AMP-activated protein kinase. *Cell Metab.* 2005; 2:9–19. [PubMed: 16054095]
11. Woods A, Dickerson K, Heath R, Hong SP, Momcilovic M, Johnstone SR, Carlson M, Carling D. Ca²⁺/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase kinase-beta acts upstream of AMP-activated protein kinase in mammalian cells. *Cell Metab.* 2005; 2:21–33. [PubMed: 16054096]
12. Brennan CM, Steitz JA. HuR and mRNA stability. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 2001; 58:266–277. [PubMed: 11289308]
13. Wang W, Yang X, Cristofalo VJ, Holbrook NJ, Gorospe M. Loss of HuR is linked to reduced expression of proliferative genes during replicative senescence. *Mol Cell Biol.* 2001; 21:5889–5898. [PubMed: 11486028]
14. Mato JM, Lu SC. Role of S-adenosyl-L-methionine in liver health and injury. *Hepatology.* 2007; 45:1306–1312. [PubMed: 17464973]

15. Mato JM, Martínez-Chantar ML, Lu SC. Methionine metabolism and liver disease. *Ann Rev Nutr.* 2008; 28:273–93. [PubMed: 18331185]
16. Lu SC, Alvarez L, Huang ZZ, Chen L, An W, Corrales FJ, Avila MA, Kanel G, Mato JM. Methionine adenosyltransferase 1A knockout mice are predisposed to liver injury and exhibit increased expression of genes involved in proliferation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2001; 98:5560–5565. [PubMed: 11320206]
17. Martínez-Chantar ML, Corrales FJ, Martínez-Cruz A, García-Trevijano ER, Huang ZZ, Chen L, Kanel G, Avila MA, Mato JM, Lu SC. Spontaneous oxidative stress and liver tumors in mice lacking methionine adenosyltransferase 1A. *FASEB J.* 2002; 16:1292–1294. [PubMed: 12060674]
18. Cai J, Mao Z, Hwang J, Lu SC. Differential expression of methionine adenosyltransferase genes influences the rate of growth of human hepatocellular carcinoma cells. *Cancer Res.* 1998; 58:1444–1450. [PubMed: 9537246]
19. Garcea R, Daino L, Pascale R, Simile MM, Puddu M, Ruggiu ME, Seddaiu MA, Satta G, Sequenza MJ, Feo F. Protooncogene methylation and expression in regenerating liver and preneoplastic liver nodules induced in the rat by diethylnitrosamine: effect of variations of S-adenosylmethionine:S-adenosylhomocysteine ratio. *Carcinogenesis.* 1989; 10:1183–1192. [PubMed: 2472229]
20. Huang ZZ, Mao Z, Cai J, Lu SC. Changes in methionine adenosyltransferase during liver regeneration in the rat. *Am J Physiol.* 1998; 275:G14–G21. [PubMed: 9655679]
21. Pascale RM, Simile MM, Daino L, Pinna G, Bennati S, Carta M, Seddaiu MA, Massarelli G, Feo F. Chemoprevention of rat liver carcinogenesis by S-adenosyl-L-methionine: a long term study. *Cancer Res.* 1995; 16:427–430.
22. Hortelano S, Dewez B, Genaro AM, Díaz-Guerra MJ, Boscá L. Nitric oxide is raised in regenerating liver after partial hepatectomy. *Hepatology.* 1995; 21:776–786. [PubMed: 7533126]
23. Díaz-Guerra MJ, Velasco M, Martín-Sanz P, Boscá L. Nuclear factor kappaB is required for the transcriptional control of type II NO synthase in regenerating liver. *Biochem J.* 1997; 326:791–797. [PubMed: 9307029]
24. Rai RM, Lee FY, Rosen A, Tang SQ, Lin HZ, Koteish A, Liew FY, Zaragoza C, Lowenstein C, Diehl AM. Impaired liver regeneration in inducible nitric oxide synthase deficient mice. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 1998; 95:1329–1334.
25. Ruiz F, Corrales FJ, Miqueo C, Mato JM. Nitric oxide inactivates rat hepatic methionine adenosyltransferase In vivo by S-nitrosylation. *Hepatology.* 1998; 28:1051–1057. [PubMed: 9755242]
26. Pérez-Mato I, Castro C, Ruiz FA, Corrales FJ, Mato JM. Methionine adenosyltransferase S-nitrosylation is regulated by the basic and acidic amino acids surrounding the target thiol. *J Biol Chem.* 1999; 274:17075–17079. [PubMed: 10358060]
27. Chen ZP, Mitchellhill KI, Michel BJ, Stapleton D, Roriguez-Crespo I, Witters LA, Power DA, Ortiz de Montellano PR, Kemp BE. AMP-activated protein kinase phosphorylation of endothelial NO synthase. *FEBS Lett.* 1999; 29:285–289. [PubMed: 10025949]
28. Morrow VA, Foufelle F, Connell JM, Petrie JR, Gould GW, Salt IP. Direct activation of AMP-activated protein kinase stimulates nitric-oxide synthesis in human aortic endothelial cells. *J Biol Chem.* 2003; 278:31629–31639. [PubMed: 12791703]
29. Levine YC, Li GK, Michel T. Agonist-modulated regulation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) in endothelial cells. Evidence for an AMPK>Rac1>Akt>endothelial nitric-oxide synthase pathway. *J Biol Chem.* 2007; 282:20351–20364. [PubMed: 17519230]
30. Reihill JA, Ewart MA, Hardie DG, Salt IP. AMP-activated protein kinase mediates VEGF-stimulated endothelial NO production. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2007; 354:1084–1088. [PubMed: 17276402]
31. Makondo K, Kimura K, Kitamura T, Yamaji D, Jung BD, Saito M. Hepatocyte growth factor activates endothelial nitric oxide synthase by Ca(2+)- and phosphoinositide 3-kinase/Akt-dependent phosphorylation in aortic endothelial cells. *Biochem J.* 2003; 374:63–69. [PubMed: 12757411]
32. Uruno A, Sugawara A, Kanatsuka H, Arima S, Taniyama Y, Kudo M, Takeuchi K, Ito S. Hepatocyte growth factor stimulates nitric oxide production through endothelial nitric oxide synthase activation by the phosphoinositide 3-kinase/Akt pathway and possibly by mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase in vascular endothelial cells. *Hypertens Res.* 2004; 27:887–895. [PubMed: 15824471]
33. Wang HH, Lautt WW. Evidence of nitric oxide, a flow-dependent factor, being a trigger of liver regeneration in rats. *Can J Physiol Pharmacol.* 1998; 76:1072–1079. [PubMed: 10326828]
34. García-Trevijano ER, Martínez-Chantar ML, Latasa MU, Mato JM, Avila MA. NO sensitizes rat hepatocytes to proliferation by modifying S-adenosylmethionine levels. *Gastroenterology.* 2002; 122:1355–1363. [PubMed: 11984522]
35. Gobeil F, Zhu T, Brault S, Geha A, Vazquez-Tello A, Fortier A, Barbaz D, Checchin D, Hou X, Nader M, Bkaily G, Gratton J-P, Heveker N, Ribeiro-da-Silva A, Peri K, Bard H, Chorvatova A, D'Orleans-Juste P, Goetzl EJ, Chemtob S. Nitric oxide signaling via nuclearized endothelial nitric-oxide synthase expression of the immediate early genes iNOS and mPGES-1. *J Biol Chem.* 2006; 281:16058–16067. [PubMed: 16574649]
36. Leffert HL, Koch KS, Moran T, Williams M. Liver cells. *Methods Enzymol.* 1979; 58:536–544. [PubMed: 423789]
37. Medico E, Mongioli AM, Huff J, Jelinek MA, Follenzi A, Gaudino G, Parsons JT, Comoglio PM. The tyrosine kinase receptors Ron and Sea control scattering and morphogenesis of liver progenitor cells in vitro. *Mol Biol Cell.* 1996; 7:495–504. [PubMed: 8730094]
38. López-Rivera E, Lizarbe TR, Martínez-Moreno M, López-Novoa JM, Rodríguez-Barbero A, Rodrigo J, Fernández AP, Alvarez-

- Barrientos A, Lamas S, Zaragoza C. Matrix metalloproteinase 13 mediates nitric oxide activation of endothelial cell migration. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2005; 102:3685–3690. [PubMed: 15728377]
39. Higgins BC, Andersen RM. Experimental pathology of liver: restoration of liver of the white rat following partial surgical removal. *Arch Pathol*. 1931; 12:186–202.
 40. Martínez-Chantar ML, Vazquez-Chantada M, Ariz U, Martínez N, Varela M, Capdevila A, Rodríguez J, Aransay AM, Matthiesen R, Yang H, Calvisi DF, Esteller M, Fraga M, Lu SC, Mato JM. Loss of the glycine N-methyltransferase gene leads to steatosis and hepatocellular carcinoma in mice. *Hepatology*. 2008; 28:273–293.
 41. Sapkota GP, Kieloch A, Lizcano JM, Lain S, Arthur JS, Williams MR, Morrice N, Deak M, Alessi DR. Phosphorylation of the protein kinase mutated in Peutz-Jeghers cancer syndrome, LKB1/ STK11, at Ser431 by p90(RSK) and cAMP-dependent protein kinase, but not its farnesylation at Cys(433), is essential for LKB1 to suppress cell growth. *J Biol Chem*. 2001; 276:19469–19482. [PubMed: 11297520]
 42. Frémin C, Ezan F, Boisselier P, Bessard A, Pagès G, Pouysségur J, Baffet G. ERK2 but not ERK1 plays a key role in hepatocyte replication: an RNAi-mediated ERK2 knockdown approach in wild-type and ERK1 null hepatocytes. *Hepatology*. 2007; 45:1035–1045. [PubMed: 17393467]
 43. Majano PL, García-Monzón C, García-Trevijano ER, Corrales FJ, Cámara J, Ortiz P, Mato JM, Avila MA, Moreno-Otero R. S-Adenosylmethionine modulates inducible nitric oxide synthase gene expression in rat liver and isolated hepatocytes. *J Hepatol*. 2001; 35:692–699. [PubMed: 11738094]
 44. McCall TB, Feelisch M, Palmer RM, Moncada S. Identification of N-iminoethyl-L-ornithine as an irreversible inhibitor of nitric oxide synthase in phagocytic cells. *Br J Pharmacol*. 1991; 102:234–238. [PubMed: 1710525]
 45. Chen L, Zeng Y, Yang H, Le TD, French SW, Corrales FJ, García-Trevijano ER, Avila MA, Mato JM, Lu SC. Impaired liver regeneration in mice lacking methionine adenosyltransferase 1A. *FASEB J*. 2004; 18:914–916. [PubMed: 15033934]
 46. Latasa MU, Boukaba A, García-Trevijano ER, Torres L, Rodríguez JL, Caballería J, Lu SC, López-Rodas G, Franco L, Mato JM, Avila MA. Hepatocyte growth factor induces MAT2A expression and histone acetylation in rat hepatocytes: role in liver regeneration. *FASEB J*. 2001; 15:1248–1250. [PubMed: 11344103]
 47. Rodríguez-Pascual F, Hausding M, Ihrig-Biedert I, Furneaux H, Levy AP, Förstermann U, Kleinert H. Complex contribution of the 3'-untranslated region to the expressional regulation of the human inducible nitric-oxide gene. Involvement of the RNA-binding protein HuR. *J Biol Chem*. 2000; 275:26040–26049. [PubMed: 10859327]
 48. Matsui K, Nishizawa M, Ozaki T, Kimura T, Hashimoto I, Yamada M, Kaibori M, Kamiyama Y, Ito S, Okumura T. Natural antisense transcript stabilizes inducible nitric oxide synthase messenger RNA in rat hepatocytes. *Hepatology*. 2008; 47:686–697. [PubMed: 18161049]
 49. Choi HC, Song P, Xie Z, Wu Y, Xu J, Zhang M, Dong Y, Wang S, Lau K, Zou MH. Reactive nitrogen species is required for the activation of the AMP-activated protein kinase by statin in vivo. *J Biol Chem*. 2008; 283:20186–20197. [PubMed: 18474592]
 50. Nakashima S, Saji S, Nakamura T, Nozawa Y. Activated protein kinase activation in hepatocyte growth factor-stimulated rat hepatocytes: involvement of protein tyrosine kinase and protein kinase C. *Hepatology*. 1996; 23:1244–1253. [PubMed: 8621160]
 51. Hashigasako A, Machide M, Nakamura T, Matsumoto K, Nakamura T. Bidirectional regulation of Ser-985 phosphorylation of c-Met via protein kinase C and protein phosphatase 2A involves c-Met activation and cellular responsiveness to hepatocyte growth factor. *J Biol Chem*. 2004; 279:26445–26452. [PubMed: 15075332]

ABBREVIATIONS: (SAdMe) S-adenosylmethionine, AMPK (AMP-activated protein kinase), HCC (hepatocellular carcinoma), HGF (hepatocyte growth factor), MAT(methionine adenosyltransferase), eNOS (endothelial nitric oxide synthase), iNOS (inducible nitric oxide synthase), NO (nitric oxide), PH (partial hepatectomy).

Figure 1. HGF Induces the Phosphorylation of LKB1, AMPK, and eNOS Through a Process Inhibited by SAME. a) Mouse hepatocytes were incubated for 1-or 4-hours in the presence or absence of HGF (25 ng/ml) and, at the end of this period, cell extracts (30 μ g per lane) were analyzed by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. **b)** Mouse hepatocytes were preincubated in the presence or absence of the ERK1/2 inhibitor U0126 (50 μ mol/L) for 2-hours. At the end of this period cells were treated with buffer only or HGF (25 ng/ml). Cells extracts were collected 1-hour later and analyzed by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. **c)** Mouse hepatocytes were incubated for 4-hours with HGF (25 ng/ml), HGF + SAME (4 mmol/L), SAME alone, or HGF + L-NAME (2 mmol/L). Cell extracts were collected and analyzed by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. **d)** Mouse hepatocytes were incubated as described in (c). Calyculin A (5 nmol/L), an inhibitor of PP2A and PP1, was added 30 minutes before other additives, and the cell extract analyzed by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. Figure shows a representative experiment carried out four times.

Figure 2. Identification of P-eNOS in Primary Mouse Hepatocytes by Confocal Microscopy. Hepatocytes were incubated with HGF (25 ng/ml) and/or SAMe (4mM) for 1-hour. Cells were fixed with ethanol and incubated overnight with a P-eNOS Ser 1177 antibody (red). Nuclei were stained with Dapi (blue).

Figure 3. HGF-mediated LKB1/AMPK/eNOS Phosphorylation and Proliferation in Hepatocytes is Inhibited by NIO. a) Mouse hepatocytes were incubated for 4-hours with HGF (25 ng/ml), HGF + NIO (1 mmol/L), or NIO alone. The cell extract (30 μ g per lane) was collected and analyzed by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. Figure shows a representative experiment carried out four times. **b)** Mouse hepatocytes were treated with buffer only (control), HGF (25 ng/ml), HGF + L-NAME (2 mmol/L) or HGF + NIO (1mmol/L) for another 24-hours, the last 10-hours also with (3 H)-thymidine, and the synthesis of DNA was determined. *Denotes significant level of difference ($p < 0.05$) vs. control (a) or HGF treated hepatocytes (b). Figure shows the average of four experiments in triplicate.

Figure 4. HGF-mediated eNOS phosphorylation is downstream LKB1 and AMPK phosphorylation. MLP29 cells were transfected with 100 nmol/L control iRNA, or with LKB1-, AMPK α 1-, or eNOS-specific iRNA using oligofectamine reagent for 24-hours. **a)** Immunoblots of LKB1, AMPK α 1 and eNOS protein expression. **b)** Forty-eight hours after transfection, cells were treated with buffer only (control) or with HGF (25 ng/ml) for 4-hours. The cell extract (30 μ g per lane) was collected and analyzed by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. Figure shows a representative experiment carried out four times.

Figure 5. Knockdown of LKB1, AMPK or eNOS with iRNA inhibits HGF-mediated proliferation. MLP29 cells were transfected with 100 nmol/L control iRNA, or with LKB1-, AMPK α 1-, or eNOS-specific iRNA using oligofectamine reagent for 24-hours as in Figure 4. Twenty-four hours after transfection, cells were treated with buffer only (control) or with HGF (25 ng/ml) for another 24-hours, the last 14-hours also with (3 H)-thymidine, and the synthesis of DNA determined. Figure shows the average of four experiments in triplicate. *Denotes significant level of difference ($p < 0.05$) vs. MLP29 cells transfected with control iRNA and stimulated with HGF.

Figure 6. Phosphorylation of LKB1, AMPK and eNOS during liver regeneration after partial hepatectomy. a) Partial hepatectomy (PH) was carried out in wild-type (WT) mice. Liver samples were obtained before, 30 minutes, 1- and 24-hours after PH and analyzed (30 μ g per lane) by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. Figure shows a representative experiment carried out four times. **b)** PH was carried out in WT mice, knockout mice deficient in hepatic SAME (MAT1A-KO), WT animals pre-treated with SAME (WT + SAME, 50mg/kg i.p. SAME, 3 times at 12 hours interval, last dose 30 min before hepatectomy), and in eNOS knockout mice (eNOS-KO). Liver samples were obtained before and twenty-four hours after PH and analyzed (30 μ g per lane) by Western blotting with the indicated antibodies. Figure shows a representative experiment carried out four times. **c)** Hepatocyte proliferation after PH as assessed by BrdU incorporation. The number of BrdU positive cells at time 0-hours and 48-hours after PH were counted and expressed as a percentage of the total number of cells present per section. Ratio between percentage at 48-hours and 0-hours was calculated for WT \pm SAME, eNOS-KO and WT mice. Figure shows the average of four experiments in triplicate. *Denotes significant level of difference ($p < 0.05$) vs. WT liver samples 48 hours after PH.

Figure 7. Model of an LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade regulated by HGF, SAmE and NO implicated in hepatocyte proliferation. HGF/MET induces the phosphorylation and activation of LKB1, AMPK, and eNOS. AMPK phosphorylation induces the translocation to cytoplasm of HuR (HuRc), an RNA-binding protein that induces cell cycle progression and hepatocyte proliferation by increasing the half-life of target mRNAs such as cyclin A2 and cyclin D1. HuR also binds and stabilizes iNOS. eNOS-dependent NO production activates iNOS induction, which further contributes to NO synthesis, and methionine adenosyltransferase I/III (MAT I/III) inactivation, the main enzyme responsible of hepatic SAmE synthesis. This reduction in hepatic SAmE synthesis prevents the activation of phosphoprotein phosphatases (PPase), which further increases the phosphorylation and activation of the LKB1/AMPK/eNOS cascade and hepatocyte proliferation. NIO and L-NAME inhibit HGF-mediated hepatocyte proliferation via inhibition of NO synthesis and of the blocking effect this molecule exerts on SAmE production, PPase activation and the inactivation of LKB1 and AMPK. SAmE inhibits HGF-mediated hepatocyte proliferation via activation of PPase and inactivation of LKB1, AMPK and eNOS.